

**REPRESENTATION OF THE NUMBER IN THE NUMBER SYSTEM OF
10 AS SUM OF THE LEVELS OF 3.****Ghafforov Husayn Aliyarovich****Termiz State Pedagogical Institute, teacher of the Department of
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Annotation: This article examines the proof that arbitrary numbers in the 10-digit number system can be expressed as powers of 3.

Keyword: powers of 3, remainder, sum, proof, summary.

Theorem: Numbers in any arbitrary 10-digit number system can be expressed as a sum of powers of 3.

Proof: Let's calculate the proof of this theorem using several problems.

Issue 1. Express the number 10283 in the number system of 10 as a sum of powers of 3?

Solution:

$10283 \div 3 = 3427$	(2 <i>qoldiq</i>)
$3427 \div 3 = 1142$	(1 <i>qoldiq</i>)
$1142 \div 3 = 380$	(2 <i>qoldiq</i>)
$380 \div 3 = 126$	(2 <i>qoldiq</i>)
$126 \div 3 = 42$	(0 <i>qoldiq</i>)
$42 \div 3 = 14$	(0 <i>qoldiq</i>)
$14 \div 3 = 4$	(2 <i>qoldiq</i>)
$4 \div 3 = 1$	(1 <i>qoldiq</i>)
$1 \div 3 = 0$	(1 <i>qoldiq</i>)

$$\begin{aligned}
(10283)_{10} &= (112002212)_3 = 1*3^8 + 1*3^7 + (3-1)*3^6 + 0 + 0 + (3-1)*3^3 + \\
&(3-1)*3^2 + 3^1 + (3-1)*3^0 = 3^8 + 3^7 + 3^7 - 3^6 + 3^4 - 3^3 - 3^3 - 3^2 + 3^1 + 3^1 - 3^0 = \\
\text{a)} &= 3^8 + (3-1)*3^7 - 3^6 + 3^4 - (3-1)*3^3 - 3^2 + (3-1)*3^1 - 3^0 = \\
&= 3^8 + 3^8 - 3^7 - 3^6 + 3^4 - 3^4 + 3^3 - 3^2 + 3^2 - 3^1 - 3^0 = (3-1)*3^8 - \\
&-3^7 - 3^6 + 3^3 - 3^1 - 3^0 = 3^9 - 3^8 - 3^7 - 3^6 + 3^3 - 3^1 - 3^0
\end{aligned}$$

Issue 2. Express the number 283 in the number system of 10 as a sum of powers of 3?

Solution:

$$\begin{aligned}
283 \div 3 &= 94 \quad (1 \text{ qoldiq}) \\
94 \div 3 &= 31 \quad (1 \text{ qoldiq}) \\
31 \div 3 &= 10 \quad (1 \text{ qoldiq}) \\
10 \div 3 &= 3 \quad (1 \text{ qoldiq}) \\
3 \div 3 &= 1 \quad (0 \text{ qoldiq}) \\
1 \div 3 &= 0 \quad (1 \text{ qoldiq})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{a) } (283)_{10} = (101111)_3 = 1*3^5 + 0 + 1*3^3 + 1*3^2 + 1*3^1 + 1*3^0 = 3^5 + 3^3 + 3^2 + 3^1 + 3^0$$

Issue 3. Express the number 27139 in the number system of 10 as a sum of powers of 3?

Solution:

$$\begin{aligned}
27139 \div 3 &= 9046 \quad (1 \text{ qoldiq}) \\
9046 \div 3 &= 3015 \quad (1 \text{ qoldiq}) \\
3015 \div 3 &= 1005 \quad (0 \text{ qoldiq}) \\
1005 \div 3 &= 335 \quad (0 \text{ qoldiq}) \\
335 \div 3 &= 111 \quad (2 \text{ qoldiq}) \\
111 \div 3 &= 37 \quad (0 \text{ qoldiq}) \\
37 \div 3 &= 12 \quad (1 \text{ qoldiq}) \\
12 \div 3 &= 4 \quad (0 \text{ qoldiq}) \\
4 \div 3 &= 1 \quad (1 \text{ qoldiq}) \\
1 \div 3 &= 0 \quad (1 \text{ qoldiq})
\end{aligned}$$

$$(27139)_{10} = (1101020011)_3 = 1*3^9 + 1*3^8 + 0 + 1*3^6 + 0 + (3-1)*3^4 + 0 + 0 + 1*3^1 + 1*3^0 =$$

a)

$$= 3^9 + 3^8 + 3^6 + 3^5 - 3^4 + 3^1 + 3^0$$

Issue 4. Express the number 45058 in the number system of 10 as a sum of powers of 3?

Solution:

$$\begin{array}{ll} 45058 \div 3 = 15019 & (1 \text{ qoldiq}) \\ 15019 \div 3 = 5006 & (1 \text{ qoldiq}) \\ 5006 \div 3 = 1668 & (2 \text{ qoldiq}) \\ 1668 \div 3 = 556 & (0 \text{ qoldiq}) \\ 556 \div 3 = 185 & (1 \text{ qoldiq}) \\ 185 \div 3 = 61 & (2 \text{ qoldiq}) \\ 61 \div 3 = 20 & (1 \text{ qoldiq}) \\ 20 \div 3 = 6 & (2 \text{ qoldiq}) \\ 6 \div 3 = 2 & (0 \text{ qoldiq}) \\ 2 \div 3 = 0 & (2 \text{ qoldiq}) \end{array}$$

$$(45058)_{10} = (2021210211)_3 = (3-1)*3^9 + 0 + (3-1)*3^7 + 1*3^6 + (3-1)*3^5 + 1*3^4 +$$

a)

$$0 + (3-1)*3^2 + 1*3^1 + 1*3^0 = 3^{10} - 3^9 + 3^8 - 3^7 + 3^6 + 3^6 - 3^5 + 3^4 + 3^3 - 3^2 + 3^1 + 3^0 =$$

$$3^{10} - 3^9 + 3^8 - 3^7 + (3-1)*3^6 - 3^5 + 3^4 + 3^3 - 3^2 + 3^1 + 3^0 = 3^{10} - 3^9 + 3^8 - 3^7 + 3^7 - 3^6 -$$

$$-3^5 + 3^4 + 3^3 - 3^2 + 3^1 + 3^0 = 3^{10} - 3^9 + 3^8 - 3^6 - 3^5 + 3^4 + 3^3 - 3^2 + 3^1 + 3^0$$

Issue 5. Express the number 98 in the number system of 10 as a sum of powers of 3?

Solution:

$$\begin{array}{ll} 98 \div 3 = 32 & (2 \text{ qoldiq}) \\ 32 \div 3 = 10 & (2 \text{ qoldiq}) \\ 10 \div 3 = 3 & (1 \text{ qoldiq}) \\ 3 \div 3 = 1 & (0 \text{ qoldiq}) \\ 1 \div 3 = 0 & (1 \text{ qoldiq}) \end{array}$$

$$(98)_{10} = (10122)_3 = 1 \cdot 3^4 + 0 \cdot 3^3 + 1 \cdot 3^2 + (3-1) \cdot 3^1 + (3-1) \cdot 3^0 = 3^4 + 3^2 + 3^2 - 3^1 + 3^1 - 3^0 =$$

a)

$$= 3^4 + (3-1) \cdot 3^2 - 3^0 = 3^4 + 3^3 - 3^2 - 3^0$$

The theorem was proved using the above 5 problems.

So, we can come to the following conclusion: any number in the 10-digit number system can be expressed as a sum of powers of 3.

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